

2023

Conference Proceedings
Egham, England

International scientific and practical Conference

MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH

Conference proceedings available
at virtualconference.press

Institute for Scientific Research and Publication

Independent Publishing Network

Modern views and research – 2023

Chief Editor: R.Shilton

Independent Publishing Network Ltd

Mailing address – MB #1869, PO BOX 229, EGHAM, TW20
8WZ, UK

Registered Office – 71-75 Shelton Street, Covent Garden,
London, WC2H 9JQ, UK

International scientific and practical Conference

Modern views and research - 2023: Egham. Independent
Publishing Network Ltd.

Date signed for printing,

For students, research workers

ISBN 978-1-83853-487-5

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811329>

Publisher:Independent Publishing Network.

© Authors, 2023

© Independent Publishing Network Ltd

Modern views and research - 2023

The collection of scientific papers available on
Virtualconferences.press

January March 2023

Company Number 11541223

MEDICAL SCIENCE

New composite plate for hemostasis in parenchymatous organs surgery

**Abdullazhanov B.R., Babadzhanov A.Kh., Saliev G.Z.
Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center
for Surgery named after acad. V. Vakhidov
Andijan State Medical Institute**

As a result of injuries of the abdominal cavity or extended surgical interventions, extensive wound defects are often formed, the restoration of which with the usage of local tissues is not seen possible. This leads to the development of a number of complications such as: bleeding, lymphorrhea, prolonged healing, infection, adhesion formation, and others. Injuries lead to 10% of all deaths worldwide, and blood loss is the most common preventable cause of death after injury. Bleeding and hemorrhagic shock are responsible for 30-40% of traumatic deaths.

There is a need to develop unique hemostatic medications that can deliver a hemostatic agent in a few seconds and stop bleeding within two minutes at the site of injury, without any intervention in the form of manual pressure on the wound area or any special training for their application. There is also a need to develop more hemostatic agents that can remain functional for longer periods without the need for replacement. Based on this, more research is needed to analyze performance closer to "real world" situations, which often require unique and personalized injuries and clinical settings.

We have developed a version of the hemostatic film, which has a complex composition and is a composite material.

The main composition of the composite material are cellulose derivatives:

- A layer that provides high adhesion to the wet surface of biological tissues and is a film of Na-CMC (85%) + Ca²⁺ ions at a concentration (15%) with a thickness of 50 microns;
- The second layer is a reinforced hemostatic layer which includes Na-CMC (63%) + oxidized viscose (12%) + Ca²⁺ ions (25%). In the second layer there are fibers of oxidized viscose with a thread thickness of up to 25 microns, with a distance between the fibers of 500-1000 microns;

- The outer layer is a hydrophobic film up to 10 microns thick made from vegetable oil (cotton oil).

Viscose fiber is extracted by processing natural plant cellulose and is considered a modification of cellulose fiber called rayon cellulose. In our study, the native state of both fibers was assessed using a stereomicroscope (MBS-2 LOMO).

At the same time, viscose, when visually inspected, is free of defects, smooth, transparent, the thickness of the fibers is the same. Cotton cellulose fiber consists of many small fibers and is not smooth. The thickness is not the same along the length of the thread and varies unevenly.

When studying the effect of oxidants (oxidizing agent - 12% sodium hypochlorite solution) on the tensile strength of the fibers that make up the composite coating, it was found that the breakage of the viscose fiber increases with time, and the force expended on breaking decreases. Compared to cellulose fibre. The results are presented in the form of a table and a histogram.

Under the influence of oxidants, both fibers changed in different ways. Cotton cellulose showed high resistance, the degree of fiber breakage decreased by only 1.5 times in 4 hours. Viscose fiber lost strength 3 times in 3 hours, completely disintegrated by 4 hours.

Fiber adhesion was also evaluated. As a result of tests, it was found that the adhesive ability of the viscose composite material is 961 pascals (Pa).

Visual and stereomicroscopic evaluation of the new composite coating shows that the fibers are distributed in the center of the composite film and form an integral whole with other components of the film. When viewed under a stereomicroscope, the gauze fibers completely retained their mesh structure. Film thickness was 2 mm. The results obtained were calculated using the following formula: adhesive strength (F): $F = mg$. Here m is the mass, g is the free fall acceleration of $9.8 \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}$. The stickiness was then calculated: F/S . Ra (Pascal) was chosen as the unit of measurement. The test substance, cut into $1 \text{ cm} * 1 \text{ cm}$ on the surface of the device, was evenly mixed with $100 \mu\text{l}$ of water. The lifting threads were attached to the attached coverslip with a small thread. Waited one minute, then attached to the

clamp, experimented with changing the weight and studied it by adding water to the wetted part of the equipment. In this case, the density of water was assumed to be 1 g/cm³.

In a comparative aspect, among various variants of cellulose-based biomaterials, it has been established that the inclusion of oxidized viscose in the composition provides an improvement in the physicochemical properties of the composite hemostatic film, including the best tensile strength, adhesion to the surface of the isolated liver, and also in the presence of blood and plasma, hygroscopic and bactericidal.

Thus, the developed plate has a very high adhesive ability to a wet surface, the degree of which can stop not only capillary, but also mixed bleeding from parenchymal organs. The possibility of having a hemostatic property is justified by the results of in vitro studies, which showed that the composite hemostatic film shortens the blood clotting time, which, therefore, indicates an increase in the overall coagulation activity of whole blood. This will allow it to be used as a local hemostatic agent.

Surgical tactics of patients with post-burn extension cicatricial contracture of fingers

Askhanov Z.P.

Andijan State Medical Institute

The authors analyzed the results of the applied surgical tactics in 17 patients with post-burn extensor cicatricial contracture of the fingers.

The authors concluded that necrosis of the flap tip is common in 25% of cases with Limberg plasty, and the application of an O-shaped suture increases the viability of the flap tip to 88.2%.

Key words: post-burn contractures, extensor contractures, post-burn scars, surgical tactics, contractures of fingers.

Introduction. With extensive burns, occupying more than 30% of the body surface, there are always burns of the hands. Hand burns account for 5.1-6.5% of injuries [1,2]. Hand deformities after burns occur in 40-50% of patients, in 22.5% of cases they become the cause of disability [3,4,5]. Therefore, one of the most urgent and complex problems in the rehabilitation of burnt patients is the restoration of hand functions.

The aim of the research – to study the results of surgical tactics in patients with post-burn extensor cicatricial contracture of the fingers.

Materials and methods. The work is based on the results of surgical treatment of 17 patients who were treated in the department of reconstructive surgery of the multidisciplinary medical center in Andijan region.

Results. Opposite-flap plasty is similarly based on the movement of two or more adjacent triangular-shaped flaps, which consist of skin and deep subcutaneous adipose tissue.

Stages of surgery: after anesthesia, the operating field is treated with antiseptic solutions, soft tissues are hydroprepared from deep structures, then a longitudinal incision of the scar is made along the ridge of the tightening cicatricial fold at an acute angle of 60-70°, it is split into 2 sheets in the form of a triangle, also with additional lateral incisions to the first, tissue tension is removed and a second

triangular flap is formed. The upper corners of the flap on both sides of the triangles are the same in depth and thickness of the incisions. The length of the lateral and longitudinal incisions depends on the size of the cicatricial fold and the shortening of the tissues caused by it. Hemostasis should be point. In the next step, the triangular flaps are reversed. The resulting wound is closed and sutured with interrupted sutures, the difference is that, the needle injection begins with a defect in the recipient zone, then subdermally passes the end of the flap, then it is removed parallel to the first injection of the needle from the recipient zone of the defect. The proposed methods of applying an O-shaped seam. The operation ends with an antiseptic bandage and a plaster splint. To gradually restore the microcirculation of the flap, we performed hypothermia for 1-4 days.

In the immediate postoperative period, necrosis of the end of the flap was noted in 1 (5.8%) of 17 patients, and wound divergence in 1 (5.8%) patient. The wound healed a second time.

In the long term, 2 (11.6%) of 17 patients had relapses in the form of contractures. The studied shortcomings of Z-plasty were necrosis of the flap tip associated with incorrect flap formation, as well as, in our opinion, the incorrect suturing of the flap tip. Under these circumstances, we have improved the modification of the O-shaped suture. Thanks to this method, with linear scars, it is possible to immediately eliminate the deformity, and you can also get a 94.1% good functional result.

Conclusion. In Limberg plasty, necrosis of the flap tip is common in 25% of cases, the application of an O-shaped suture increases the viability of the flap tip to 88.2%.

References.

1. Liu H.F., Zhang F., Lineaweaver W.C. (2017). History and advancement of burn treatments // *Ann. Plast. Surg.* 78 S2-S8. 10.1097/SAP.0000000000000896
2. Sheckter C.C., Meyerkord N.L., Sinskey Y.L., Clark P., Anderson K., Van Vliet M. (2020). The optimal treatment for partial thickness burns: a cost-utility analysis of skin allograft vs. topical silver dressings. *J. Burn Care Res.* 41 450-456. 10.1093/jbcr/iraa003
3. Ma K., Kwon S.H., Padmanabhan J., Duscher D., Trotsyuk A.A., Dong Y., et al. (2018). Controlled delivery of a focal adhesion kinase inhibitor results in accelerated wound closure with decreased scar formation. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* 138 2452-2460. 10.1016/j.jid.2018.04.034
4. Zhu XX, Zheng Z, Zhang DM, Zhu ZS. [Effects of free transplantation of expanded perforator flaps in the treatment of severe scar contracture deformities in children]. *Zhonghua Shao Shang Za Zhi.* 2019 Jun 20;35(6):405-409. Chinese. doi: 10.3760/cma.j.issn.1009-2587.2019.06.002. PMID: 31280531.

5. Gurtner G.C., Garcia A.D., Bakewell K., Alarcon J. B. (2020). A retrospective matched-cohort study of 3994 lower extremity wounds of multiple etiologies across 644 institutions comparing a bioactive human skin allograft, TheraSkin, plus standard of care, to standard of care alone. *Int. Wound J.* 17 55-64. 10.1111/iwj.13231

Efficiency of a new composite hemostatic film in liver surgery

Babadzhanov A.Kh., Abdullazhanov B.R., Kuchkarov M.Yu.
**Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center
for Surgery named after acad. V. Vakhidov
Andijan State Medical Institute**

Relevance: Achieving a hemostatic effect by physical methods of influencing the wound surface and the parenchyma's bleeding vessels is rational mainly for its shallow and superficial injuries. To stop bleeding from parenchyma vessels with a diameter of more than 1.0 mm, an increase in exposure and power of energy exposure is required, which inevitably leads to damage to the stromal elements of the organ and increases the area of parenchyma necrosis to a depth of 4-8 mm, and the resulting coagulation eschar often serves as a substrate for infection and recurrence of bleeding. Physical methods of hemostasis during operations on parenchymal organs do not meet the requirements of the "ideal method", which should be accompanied by minimal blood loss or its absence, minimal parenchymal necrosis, and reduced operation time. In regard with this, the development of fast-acting, safe, effective and economical hemostatic materials is of great clinical and social importance.

Materials and methods: the development of a model of parenchymal bleeding among large animals (dogs, pigs) was carried out with an assessment of the effectiveness of a domestic coating - a composite plate. After the removal of the wooden coat from the anterior abdominal wall, an upper-middle-median laparotomy was performed. After dilution of the wound edges with a retractor, the right lobe of the liver was removed into the surgical field. Using an abdominal scalpel, the liver parenchyma up to 3x4 cm in area was damaged with the development of mixed bleeding. Subsequently, to the wound surface of the liver, a hemostatic sponge (control) or a hemostatic plate (experiment) was applied and held until complete hemostasis. The reliability of hemostasis was assessed by monitoring the state of the wound for 30 minutes.

Control. A hemostatic sponge made from bovine collagen manufactured by Turon Silk Farm LLC is represents a porous plate of a light yellow colour. To stop bleeding

from the liver, a 3x4 cm sized fragment was used. After drying the wound surface of the liver, the sponge was immediately applied and pressed against the wound. The sponge was held by hand pressure for 2 minutes. Subsequently, due to the lack of adhesive ability, the sponge was kept on the surface of the liver by tamponing with a gauze napkin.

The results of using a hemostatic sponge showed that even with a 5-minute exposure, only partial hemostasis was achieved from capillary vessels. While the bleeding continued from small venous vessels. In 2 cases, blood began to pour out through a blood-soaked hemostatic sponge, which served as the basis for the removal of the sponge and application of another one. After repeated use of the sponge, hemostasis was achieved within 6 minutes. It should be noted that during a 30-minute observation, there was no dense adhesion of the sponge to the wound surface of the liver. This circumstance does not exclude the risk of resumption of bleeding at a later date.

Experiment. Modeling of a planar wound of the liver with a size of 3x4 cm was made as described above. Bleeding was achieved, which had the character of mixed with abundant soaking of a gauze napkin. After drying the liver wound with a napkin, a hemostatic plate 4x5 cm in size was immediately attached to it. In the process of contact of the plate with blood, it became more flexible and was in good contact with the uneven wound surface.

After fixation for 30 seconds, adhesion to the wound surface occurred with a complete stop of bleeding. Over time, at least 30 minutes, the plate represented a transparent coating resembling a Glisson capsule in character. The wound surface was visible through the film, which made it possible to eliminate the risk of hematoma accumulation under the surface of the film. Thus, the use of a hemostatic plate in case of liver damage makes it possible within a short time (0.5-1 minute) to achieve its complete adhesion to the wound surface with a complete stop of bleeding. The effect of hemostasis is stable, minimizing the risk of recurrence of bleeding.

Discussion: The carried out experimental studies made it possible to develop the first domestic composite hemostatic film for use in surgery of parenchymal organs,

which includes several layers based on biologically absorbable polymer derivatives (cellulose, viscose and calcium), the combination of which ensures the local hemostatic efficiency of the implant. The hemostatic preparation in the form of a finely dispersed powder is made from water-soluble cellulose derivatives and has the ability to induce hemostasis within a few seconds, has the ability to actively absorb moisture, has a high adhesive ability to wet tissues. Collagen film is made from purified medical grade collagen and has weak antigenic properties. The film has a weak adhesive ability and therefore does not stick to the hands of the surgeon during use. It has the ability of biodegradation within 3-4 weeks.

While active bleeding from the surface of the parenchymal organ, at first, with the help of available methods (coagulation, stitching), active arterial bleeding from large vessels is stopped. Subsequently, the surface of the organ is dried and, with continued bleeding from small venous and capillary vessels, a hemostatic film is applied to the wound surface with an active layer and held for 1-2 minutes. The degree of pressing corresponds to the pressure in the bleeding vessel. In view of the high adhesion of the powder to the wet surface of tissues, no additional steps are required to fix the film.

Conclusion: Implemented experimental studies made it possible to develop the first domestic composite hemostatic film for use in liver surgery, which includes several layers based on biologically absorbable polymer derivatives (cellulose, viscose and calcium), the combination of which ensures the local hemostatic efficiency of the implant.

Polymorphism of aldosterone-synthasa genes in the development of fibrotic processes in cardiorenal syndrome that developed against the background of chronic heart failure

Gadayev A.G., Turaqulov R.I., Sayfullaev M.B., Eshmamatov O.F.

Toshkent medical academy

The aim of the study was to study the significance of aldosterone and aldosterone synthase gene polymorphism in the development of fibrotic processes in cardiorenal syndrome that developed against the background of chronic heart failure.

The object of the study were 120 patients with cardiorenal syndrome, which developed against the background of coronary heart disease (CHD), who were treated in the departments of cardiology, cardioreanimation and cardiorehabilitation of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

The scientific novelty of the study is as follows:

aldosterone parameters and its role in the formation of cardiorenal syndrome in CHF with different types of ejection fraction were determined;

the degree of association of aldosterone synthase gene polymorphism with markers of cardiac and renal fibrosis was studied;

the level of association between the polymorphism of the aldosterone synthase gene and various types of ejection fractions in CHF was assessed;

a comparative analysis of the effect of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists veroshpiron and eplerenone on cardiorenal syndrome was carried out.

Implementation of the results of the research. According to the results of a study of the significance of aldosterone and aldosterone synthase gene polymorphism in the development of fibrotic processes in cardiorenal syndrome that developed on the basis of chronic heart failure:

Approved and published guidelines on the topic "The role of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists in the treatment of fibrotic processes in the kidneys with cardiorenal syndrome". In these guidelines, as a result of a comparative study of the effect of veroshpiron and eplerenone on the processes of fibrosis in the heart and

kidneys in patients with CHF, a differentiated approach to treatment in medical practice was created.

The results of the study have been put into practice at the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy, the departments of cardiology, cardiac resuscitation and cardiac rehabilitation, the multidisciplinary medical center of the Samarkand region. The introduction of the obtained scientific results into medical practice has made it possible to reduce the time for diagnosis and treatment of cardiorenal syndrome that developed against the background of chronic heart failure, as well as to prevent its complications.

Disturbances in rheological properties of peripheral blood in patients with acute rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection

Ismoilov Iskandar Ibrohimovich

assistant

Shamsiev Djakhangir Fazlitdinovich

DSc, assistant professor

Tashkent State Dental Institute. Tashkent. Uzbekistan

Abstract. The results of studying the rheological properties of blood in 75 patients with acute rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection are presented. The following main parameters were determined in patients: blood viscosity, erythrocyte aggregation coefficient, degree of erythrocyte deformability, average volume of one erythrocyte, hematocrit, fibrinogen, morphological properties of erythrocytes. In all examined patients with acute rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection, the rheological properties of the blood are sharply impaired. The severity of violations of the rheological properties of blood depended not only on the type of disease, but on its severity and the degree of intoxication of the body. A change in blood viscosity was found in all examined patients.

Indicators of blood viscosity increased sharply in proportion to the severity and prevalence of the inflammatory process and the severity of destructive changes in the affected organs.

Key words: acute rhinosinusitis, coronavirus infection, blood rheology, microcirculation

Relevance. In December 2019, a series of unexplained cases of pneumonia were reported in China. Subsequent studies have identified a new strain of coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, which is the causative agent of the acute infectious disease Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). In a short period of time, the epidemic of a new coronavirus infection has grown into a pandemic that has spread to more than 200 countries around the world. In the new millennium, humanity is faced with infectious diseases that no one knew about. Plague and typhoid were replaced by dangerous viruses. COVID-19 is having an unprecedented impact on communities around the world. The study of the pathogenesis of purulent-inflammatory diseases

of the nose and paranasal sinuses is impossible without a comprehensive analysis of various homeostasis factors and, above all, the state of microcirculation, which largely depends on the rheological properties of blood. Under the general law for all forms of fluid movement, as the viscosity of the medium increases, the speed of movement decreases, and the energy costs for its movement increase. Consequently, the deterioration of the rheological properties of blood and microcirculation are directly related. Violation of microcirculation always significantly affects the development of pathological processes. However, the function of the microcirculatory system is disturbed earlier and normalized later than the clinical manifestations of the disease.

Material and research methods. In our studies, we studied the rheological properties of blood in 75 patients with rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection. The following main indicators were determined in patients: blood viscosity, erythrocyte aggregation coefficient, degree of erythrocyte deformability, average volume of one erythrocyte, hematocrit, fibrinogen, morphological properties of erythrocytes. Given that the severity of hemorheological disorders depends on the degree of intoxication and the prevalence of the inflammatory process, we divided the patients into 3 conditional groups. The first included patients with acute rhinosinusitis. The second group included patients with chronic rhinosinusitis. The third group consisted of patients with complications of acute and chronic rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection.

Comparison of the rheological parameters of the blood of patients was carried out with 20 healthy donors examined during the planned blood collection (control).

Results. In all patients with rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection, the rheological properties of the blood are sharply disturbed. The severity of violations of the rheological properties of blood depended not only on the type of disease, but on its severity and the degree of intoxication of the body. Changes in blood viscosity were found in all examined patients. The indicators of blood viscosity increased sharply in proportion to the severity and prevalence of the inflammatory process and

the severity of destructive changes in the affected organs. The most significant changes in blood viscosity were found in patients of the third group.

In all patients, a high degree of erythrocyte aggregation was reliably detected. Moreover, with an increase in the severity and prevalence of purulent-inflammatory changes, the number and size of erythrocyte aggregates (sludge syndrome) increased. In addition to the aggregation properties of erythrocytes in modern hemorheology, much attention is paid to their elasticity or the ability to reversibly deform. The deformability of erythrocytes is the most important quality, since the erythrocyte is able to pass through capillaries, the diameter of which is smaller than the diameter of the erythrocyte. In this regard, an increase in the rigidity of erythrocytes leads to an increase in blood viscosity and a violation of microcirculation.

Erythrocyte deformability was impaired in all clinical groups. The degree of deformability disorder increased in proportion to the severity of the patients' condition and reached 10.2 ± 0.169 (with a norm of 7.14 ± 0.054)

Conclusion. Thus, the analysis of the conducted studies shows that one of the main manifestations of a violation of the rheological properties of blood in rhinosinusitis after a coronavirus infection is intravascular aggregation of erythrocytes, as well as a violation of the ability of erythrocytes to reversible deformation. These disorders, as the severity of the condition increases, increase the viscosity of whole blood, which significantly impedes blood flow in microvessels.

Bibliography:

- Djakhangir Shamsiev. Laryngo-Rhino-Otologie EUFOS 2000 Abstracts (2000). The state of the erythrocytes in patients with suppurative diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses// (1(79)) Pp.29
- Djakhangir F. Shamiev (2002). Facial Paralysis in Middle Ear Surgery. *Otology & Neurotology* 23: p. S55
- Esamuratov, A. I., & Shamsiev, J. F. (2022). Tactical approaches to the surgical treatment of chronic suppurative otitis media. *British Medical Journal*, 2(5).
- Karimov, O. M., & Shamsiev, D. F. (2022). Особенности клинических проявлений заболеваний носа у больных хронической почечной недостаточностью. *Eurasian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery*, 1(1), 27-34.
- Nodir Ibatov & Djakhangir Shamsiev. (2020). Dynamics course of wound healing after rhinoplasty. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1459-1464.

- Shamsiev, D. F., Vohidov, U. N., & Karimov, O. M. (2018). Modern view on the diagnosis and treatment of chronic inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses. *Young scientist*, (5), 84-88.
- Shamsiev, D. F., Mirazizov, K. D. (2002). Endoscopic maxillary sinusotomy. *Vestnik Otorinolaringologii*, (№4), 39-40.
- Shamsiev, D. F., & Karimov, O. M. (2022). Features Of Diseases Of Nose And Paranasal Sinuses In Patients With Chronic Renal Failure. *KRS Journal of Medicine*, 2(3), 38-43.
- Shamsiev, D. F. (2009). Peculiarities of diagnosis and surgical treatment of choanal polyps. *Vestnik Otorinolaringologii*, (№5), 37-39.
- Shamsiev, D. F. (2001). Red cell rheology in patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses. *Vestnik otorinolaringologii*, (1), 22-23.
- Shamsiev, D. F. (2006). Location of the impacted tooth in the maxillary sinus. *Vestnik otorinolaringologii*, (6), 76-77.
- Shamsiev, D. F. (1998, January). Surgical treatment of regional metastasis of larynx cancer. In *British journal of cancer* (Vol. 77, pp. 21-21).
- Shamsiev D.F., Vokhidov U.N., Karimov O.M. (2018) - European science review, // [Functional and morphological features of wound healing process in the mucosa of the nose and maxillar sinuses in patients with chronic inflammatory diseases of paranasal sinuses](#) / № 5-6, Pp.225-228
- Shamsiev D.F., Vokhidov U.N., Karimov O.M. (2018) - *Young scientist*, // [Modern view on the diagnosis and treatment of chronic inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses](#)// № 5, Pp.84-88
- Shamsiev Djakhangir. (1998) Allergologie The rheological blood characteristics in patients with suppurative diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses // (Vol. 1, № 11, pp. 571).

Pathophysiological mechanisms of a patients with hypopituitarism

Kodirova T. F. 3rd year student, medical faculty of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, kadytame@gmail.com,

Department: Pathophysiology

Scientific supervisor: **Gulyamova Gulbaxor Darhanbaevna**

Relevance: Hypopituitarism is a rare, insufficiently studied disorder, it has an estimated incidence of 4.2 cases per 100,000 per year and an estimated prevalence of 45.5 cases per 100,000 (without gender difference).

Objective: To identify the pathophysiological mechanisms of development of hypopituitarism disease.

Materials and methods:

Hypopituitarism is a health condition characterized by a decrease in the production of hormones by the pituitary gland. The pathophysiology of hypopituitarism usually involves damage to the pituitary gland, which makes it unable to produce one or more hormones in a normal way.

When one or more pituitary hormones are not produced, the gland targeted by the tropic pituitary hormone has a reduced secretory action. Under normal conditions, a decrease in the action of the target gland, or a decrease in the concentration of secondary hormones, stimulates the pituitary gland to produce more of the hormone in order to strengthen the effect. This is known as negative feedback in homeostasis.

In hypopituitarism, however, the pituitary gland or some of its component secretory cells are unable to respond adequately to a decrease in target hormone levels. As a result, the action of the target glands remains low. This eventually leads to a lack of hormones produced by the target.

In contrast to the assessment of the target glands, the function of the pituitary gland is usually assessed by combining the function of the target gland with the concentration of the stimulating or tropic pituitary hormone. The concentration of the secondary hormone thyroxin in the blood, as well as that of the tropic hormone thyrotropin or thyroid stimulating hormone, are used to assess the pituitary gland's function in regulating thyroid function.

A low thyroxin level combined with an abnormally low or even normal thyrotropin level would thus indicate pituitary disease rather than thyroid disease. This is because the normal pituitary would increase the tropic hormone in response to the low thyroid hormone concentration in blood.

Results: Hypopituitarism develops after a violation of the homeostasis chain, which leads to a stop of the physiological process and breaks the chain of negative feedback. From which it follows that hormones are not released from the pituitary gland in the same way as target cells.

Conclusion: The pathophysiological process of hypopituitarism disease is damage to the pituitary gland and homeostasis disorders.

The effectiveness of the treatment of thin endometrium in uterine infertility in women with low mass weight

Komilova D.K., Magzumova N.M.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Actuality: Endometrium – unique structure of the female body intended for reproductive function. Full maturation of the endometrium, its receptivity and the ability to enter into an adequate "dialogue" with the product conception is the key to a successful onset and gestation. According to domestic and foreign authors, the prevalence of infertility reaches 10-15%, in some regions Uzbekistan - 20%, and the frequency of spontaneous miscarriage in the first trimester of pregnancy remains at the level of 16%. Decreased female fertility has many reasons, among which the share of the uterine factor of infertility in isolated or the combined variant accounts for 24-62%.

Aim: The main goal of our research is to identify the causes in infertile women with thin endometrium and eliminate them in a timely manner. Because in infertile women, this cause is often diagnosed late or remains among other causes of infertility. Body weight is especially important for endometrial hypoplasia.

Materials and method: A total of 85 infertile women with endometrial hypoplasia were included in the study, with an average age of 26 ± 8 . Our research was conducted at the Women's Health Center for 2019-2021 years. Prospective cohort randomized controlled trial.

Results: Our first cohort group A included infertile women with 55 thin endometria. The first group is further divided into 2 subgroups, is 20 out of 55 women do not have a body mass deficit, but they have endometrial hypoplasia. The remaining 35 women have low body mass and thin endometrium. There are 30 women in our second cohort group B who are infertile women with normal body mass and normal endometrium. The 20 of our women (23,5% infertility women) in our first cohort group were given low-frequency ultrasound therapy, progesterone (Duphastone) in the second phase of the menstrual cycle, and mostly vitamins in the treatment because they did not have a body mass deficit. the remaining 35 infertile women

(41.2% infertility women) were given estrogen drugs (Lenzetto, Divigil) in both phases of the menstrual cycle in addition to the above treatment because they have a body mass deficit. In our second cohort, 30 infertile women, we used vitamins, low-frequency ultrasound therapy in the treatment of endometrial hypoplasia. The results of our study show that in 20 women in our first cohort group, the incidence of pregnancy after our modern treatment was 21%. In the remaining 35 women, the figure was 88%. In our second cohort, this result ended up being 35%.

Conclusions: In summary, body weight is also important in infertile women today, which means that they are underweight or overweight, which in turn leads to hormonal imbalances. The most common cause of infertility is a thin endometrium. This modern approach to infertility treatment can reduce the number of infertile families and restore reproductive health in the future.

Literature:1. Lash, G.E. Localization of angiogenic growth factors and their receptors in the human endometrium throughout the menstrual cycle and in recurrent miscarriage /G.E. Lash, B. A. Innes, J.A.Drury // Hum. Reprod. – 2017.- Vol. 27, №1.- P.183-195.2. Lessey, B. A. Assessment of endometrial receptivity / B. A. Lessey //Fertil. Steril. - 2017. – Vol. 96, № 3. – P. 522 - 529.

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCE
General social functions of urbanization

Sayidov Kahramon Bekturdiyevich,

independent researcher, Urgench State University QSayidov@mail.ru

Annotation. In this article, it is discussed that Urbanization follows the laws of social development, and their socio-philosophical essence is the combination of human and social existence, individual and culture, subject and space through various architecture, artistic creativity, services, infrastructure and agglomerative processes under the influence of complex factors.

Keywords. Human health, socio-cultural activity, spiritual needs, urbanization, socio-cultural development, humanism, general social functions, internal features of the object, external relations, strategic tasks, national and universal cultures.

The general social functions of urbanization include:

- humanization (humanistic function);
- culturalization (cultural function);
- homogenization (unifying function);
- aggregation (agglomerative function);
- facilitation (favorable function);
- urbanization (sitization function);
- include refinement (aesthetic function).

These functions are in accordance with the tasks that are set on the agenda of general social development. Urbanization follows the laws of social development, and their socio-philosophical essence harmonizes a person with a social existence, an individual with a culture, a subject with a space through various architecture, artistic creations, services, infrastructure and agglomerative processes under the influence of complex factors. This synthesis is of humanistic importance due to its compatibility with the goal of creating the necessary conditions for human health, socio-cultural activity, and full satisfaction of spiritual needs. Urbanization does not aim to create conditions by itself, it derives this goal from general social development. The whole socio-cultural development tends towards humanism, evaluates all created things by humanistic standards. Urbanization is no exception.

The above public functions could be continued from the point of view of the object's internal characteristics, external relations, compliance with or differences from strategic tasks, subjective and objective factors, national and universal cultures, and values. In our opinion, the above functions formed as a result of the generalization of scientific conceptual ideas and the synthesis of ideas advanced in the theory of urbanization are sufficient to reveal the socio-philosophical importance of the problem. Urbanization is a product of human socio-cultural activities and research. The created socio-cultural environment and wealth go back to urbanization or shape the urbanization environment. Experts do not call urbanization "urban culture" for nothing. By this they mean that the core of urbanization is culture, cultural assets, human activities aimed at culturalizing the social environment[1]. The humanistic nature of culture, in turn, encourages urbanization to be humanistic as well. The cities, structures, infrastructures and roads that are being built should serve people. True, they are created and built by man, and man cannot create something that is his enemy. Unfortunately, there are many cases where things are built for utilitarian purposes, especially the construction of large water reservoirs around cities or nuclear power plants, high-voltage electric wires are laid over residential areas, which are far from humanistic purposes. So, in the cities, objects that are against human interests are restored. For example, NPP helps to solve the problem of supplying the city with the necessary electricity, but it also creates a security problem. Ensuring the safe operation of the NPP requires extremely large amounts of money, and nearby cities and residents are always at risk. Therefore, it is appropriate to proceed from planning, not from urbanization, but from ensuring a healthy, prosperous and happy life of a person. [2]. The humanistic function of urbanization sets the main goal of serving human interests. Sometimes the idea of creating gigantograds is far from humanistic goals. Filling gigantograds, using them to the full does not always serve an ordinary person, a person, but, on the contrary, becomes an "excessive burden" on his economy. The establishment of a gigantograd in an area where the system of communal and cultural-household services is not

sufficiently formed, and the provision of hot and even cold water is a problem, is not a rational and humanistic approach.

The function of acculturation originates from the essence of culture, socio-cultural reality, activities and services related to them, which form the core of urbanization. It is known that culture is always recognized as a set of spiritual and material assets that perform functions such as positive, moral, creativity, creation, spiritual elevation of a person[3]. So, culturalization is the process, wealth and artefacts aimed at creative and spiritual improvement of a person. From the point of view of material assets related to urbanization (such as buildings, constructions, household appliances, urban aesthetics and design. Some researchers include processes related to religion and religious belief as part of urbanization), it can be seen that urbanization is aimed at culturalizing a person, his surroundings, life and aesthetic taste. we'll see. An object never moves away from its core, the core is something that not only unites the object around it, but also makes the object to be universal, to respond to external influences, to maintain its wholeness, identity, inner integrity[4]. In fact, the nucleus tends to be "single". Because of its "singularity", it makes the object unique, whole, unique. These aspects of the core give both urbanization and culture integrity, integrity, and identity. So, through the function of culturalization, urbanization manifests itself as a unique reality on the one hand, and as a universal one on the other. Due to its uniqueness, uniqueness and universality, urbanization becomes a socio-dynamic reality in accordance with the socio-cultural development and requirements of the time. Homogenization, that is, the unifying function (unification function) arises from the tendency of urbanization to become a global reality. The word "unification" means homogenization, standardization, standardization of things and events. The unifying function of urbanization is visible in the architecture of modern cities, the transport logistics system, the types of cultural services, the basics of urban management, the operation and design of household appliances, in short, in everything. For example, a washing machine serves to free women from manual labor and save time in the United States, China, and Uzbekistan. The new technical tool created in this regard will immediately

spread throughout the world, it will be accepted as an achievement and an advantage of urbanization. Or take cities. In the 60s of the last century, the city-towns that appeared near the big cities in the USA began to appear later in Europe, Russia, Asia, and from 2019-2020 in Uzbekistan. The tendency towards gigantogradation is unification in urban planning. The aspiration of the rural lifestyle to the urban culture creates similarities between them, which are first of all manifested in the types of services, facilities, household life, clothing, design, etc.

The spread of urbanization is happening through the unification of socio-cultural life, diversity. On the one hand, this ensures the rapid popularization of socio-cultural assets, values and lifestyles, people, regardless of where they live, enjoy socio-cultural assets in the same order, thus the trend of popularization inherent in culture becomes a characteristic and sign of urbanization. However, on the other hand, homogeneity, unification threatens the diversity of ethnocultures, rural and urban peculiarities, uniqueness, sacrifices them to standards. We must not forget that the concept of "world standards" that we use today is also a threat to the uniqueness, uniqueness and diversity of ethno-cultures. Due to the agglomeration function, urbanization differs from other socio-cultural realities. Although some researchers include agglomeration as a geographical feature, its urbanization importance cannot be denied, even that it is one of the main signs of urbanization. The connection with geography is an external sign of agglomeration, while urbanization sees it as its internal feature. In our opinion, the concentration of population in one geographical space does not make agglomeration a geographical reality. If agglomeration is a geographical reality, migration must also be considered a geographical reality, but migration has never been an object or subject of geography. In the scientific literature, urbanization is considered as one of the factors causing population displacement and migration [5]. In this interpretation, migration comes as a means and a cause of urbanization processes, because experience shows that people move not to empty land, protected lands, but to places where civilization and urbanization are formed. Therefore, it is reasonable to say that migration and agglomeration do not cause urbanization, but, on the contrary, urbanization causes

migration. But the dialectical connection between them cannot be denied, the creation of a unique urbanization, ethno-cultural environment in the newly formed agglomeration is a matter of course. Because the immigrated population does not give up its national identity, it moves its language, ethnoculture and ethno-thinking to a new social space, forming a "hybrid culture" here. The agglomerative function of urbanization is when it invites and calls people from the outskirts to itself, awakens in them the desire to live and enjoy the achievements and wealth of urban culture. Urbanization is constantly driving migration. Therefore, we can also call the agglomeration function of urbanization as the agglomeration-migration function.

What makes urbanization a fascinating reality is that it creates facilities for people to live and work, to express themselves as a social entity, and to enjoy the available cultural resources. This function is called "favorable" in English language literature (creating facilities, comfortable place and opportunity). Making the social environment comfortable for human interests and interests is the social essence of urbanization. In rural areas where the central supply is not sufficiently developed, the population is dying for things necessary for themselves and their families (such as water and gas supply, street cleaning, cooking, obtaining necessary services, etc.). In the city, people are free from such worries, they live enjoying the comforts of civilization. They do not sweep the streets, carry water, cook food by digging firewood, do not heat water and wash clothes, in short, the villagers have the opportunity to enjoy and enjoy the conveniences of the deprived urbanization. It is these amenities that make the villagers envy those who live in the city. Nevertheless, some people are surprised by such conveniences. According to them, in such a way, "living on the sly" makes a person lazy, unmotivated, unfit for physical labor. Even such empty conditions cause psychological problems. Almost 27 percent of rural respondents think negatively, that is, "city amenities make a person lazy." 41 percent of those who rate the city's amenities as "positive" are. The remaining 12 percent of respondents are neutral, more precisely, supporters of "living in the countryside and working in the city." These indicators are different for district and city respondents, and they also have a tendency to favor urban urbanization and amenities (33 percent

of district respondents, 58 percent of city respondents). So, today, in social opinion, those who support the culture and amenities of the city are leading. This also shows that a person's desire to create comfort for himself is a priority, he is in favor of making his work and living conditions lighter, more beautiful and more enjoyable. At the same time, 27 percent of rural respondents (above), 26 percent of district respondents, and 14 percent of urban respondents emphasize that city amenities do not make people happy with their life and livelihood. But the closer a person is to the life of the city, the more he enjoys its amenities, the more he is inclined to urban urbanization and adapts to it. This shows that modern city life, conveniences have a priority place in social thinking. Convenience is distinguished by the fact that the function of creation allows a person to engage in intellectual activity, learning, enlightenment and spirituality. It gives a person time and opportunity to work on himself, encourages him to find new types of creative creative research. Modern cities have become the centers of creation of intellectual wealth, the factors that ensure socio-cultural development are the discoveries of cities.

CONTENTS

MEDICAL SCIENCE

Abdullazhanov B.R., Babadzhanov A.Kh., Saliev G.Z. - New composite plate for hemostasis in parenchymatous organs surgery.	3
Askhanov Z.P. - Surgical tactics of patients with post-burn extension cicatricial contracture of fingers.	6
Babadzhanov A.Kh., Abdullazhanov B.R., Kuchkarov M.Yu. - Efficiency of a new composite hemostatic film in liver surgery.	9
Gadayev A.G., Turaqulov R.I., Sayfullaev M.B., Eshmamatov O.F. - Polymorphism of aldosterone-synthasa genes in the development of fibrotic processes in cardiorenal syndrome that developed against the background of chronic heart failure.	12
Ismoilov Iskandar Ibrohimovich, Shamsiev Djakhangir Fazlitdinovich. - Disturbances in rheological properties of peripheral blood in patients with acute rhinosinusitis after coronavirus infection.	14
Kodirova T. F., Gulyamova Gulbaxor Darhanbaevna. - Pathophysiological mechanisms of a patients with hypopituitarism.	18
Komilova D.K., Magzumova N.M. - The effectiveness of the treatment of thin endometrium in uterine infertility in women with low mass weight.	20

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCE

Sayidov Kahramon Bekturdiyevich. - General social functions of urbanization.	22
--	----